

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Evaluation of Tensile Properties and Water Absorption of Abaca Fiber Thermoplastic Composite Relative to the Fiber Length, Type of Matrix and Nanoprecipitated Calcium Carbonate

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INTRODUCTION

Abaca Fiber

- Scientifically known as *Musa textilis* Nee
- Worldwide known as **Manila Hemp**
- Characteristics
 - One of the strongest natural fibers
 - Abundant in the Philippines
 - Resistant against rotting
 - Exhibits high flexural strength comparable to that of glass fiber
 - Good abrasion resistance
 - Excellent resistance from UV rays

- 76,258.38MT of Abaca produced in year **2018**
- Philippines rank first in the world production (87.17)

abaca fiber reinforced composite

METHODOLOGY

Composite A

Composite B

Composite C

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical properties of Polyethylene-abaca flour composites

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical properties of HDPE-abaca composites with varying fiber length

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical properties of HDPE-abaca fabric composites with nanoprecipitated calcium carbonate

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Water Absorption

Morphology

PE/abaca fiber composite

PE/abaca flour composite

PE/untreated abaca fabric composites

PE/untreated abaca fabric composites with 1% NPCC

PE/treated abaca fabric composites

PE/treated abaca fabric composites with 1% NPCC

CONCLUSION

1. Addition of coupling agent maleic anhydride in the system further improved the mechanical properties of the composites. Water uptake was also improved. This was due to better adhesion between the fibers and matrix.
2. Incorporation of abaca woven fabric improved the tensile strength of pure HDPE. Further improvement in alkali (NaOH) treated abaca fibers were observed.
3. 1% NPCC led to an increase in the tensile strength and modulus. The presence of NPCC reduced the composite's water absorption.
4. Woven fabrics exhibited the strongest mechanical properties, followed by milled fibers, and lastly the short fibers. Abaca flour exceeded the short fibers due to higher aspect ratio, less imperfections per fiber unit, and achieving the critical fiber length.
5. LLDPE –abaca flour exhibited low mechanical strength than HDPE-abaca flour due to different molecular structure of the matrix.

Acknowledgement

The researchers would like to thank: DOST – Industrial Technology Development Institute staff and interns for the fabrication, testing and evaluation; Korea Institute of Materials Science, South Korea for the project entitled “ Plasma-Treated Abaca Fiber Reinforced Composite for Industrial Application ” and the DOST – PCIEERD for the financial support of the project “Design and Fabrication of an Airframe for a Medium – range, short take – off and Landing UAVs”

**THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR
YOUR KIND ATTENTION**